

Contribution of Social Reformers For Upliftment of Women Education in Colonial Punjab

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Gurkiranjit Kaur Grewal

Associate Professor
Department Of History
Centre For Distance And
Online Education, Punjabi
University,
Patiala,Punjab, India

Deep Rani

Research Scholar
Department Of History
Centre For Distance And
Online Education, Punjabi
University,
Patiala, Punjab, India

Abstract

Education is essential for every human society. Social reformers paid special attention to the education of women. During the colonial period, Sikh reformers held conferences, debates to promote women's education. Different personalities opened girls' schools, colleges and technical institutes in different areas. In this paper we are exploring the work done by Sikh individuals and institutions for women education in colonial Punjab.

Keywords Education, Colonial, Reformers, Chief Khalsa Diwan, Pardah.

Introduction

No reform is possible without social consciousness and social consciousness always comes with education. Because of the importance of education, the activities of social reformers in the late 19th and early 20th centuries revolved around the central issue of raising the standard of education among their people. socio-religious reformers also had a profound impact on the educational scene as they were involved in founding and running many educational institutions. Christian missionaries and Hindu social reformers used education as a tool to improve the social status of women. The central point of the Sikh social reformer was also to raise the standard of education among Sikh women.

Aim of study

- 1.The purpose of this paper is to assess the level and nature of education in colonial Punjab.
- 2.To evaluate the work done by various social reformers in the field of education in colonial Punjab.
3. To study the efforts of Sikh social reformers to promote women's education in colonial Punjab.

Review of Literature

Though much literature and source material is available on women education, but we find very little work on Sikh women education. Therefore it needs more probing.

Brij Pal Singh in his work (*Education Progress and Economic Development in Punjab*, Punjabi University Press, Patiala, 1974) studied an educational progress and economic development in Punjab. His main analysis is that the content of education is much more important than the linear growth system. He throws focus that education provides for economic development. He also examines the professional and technical education and their impact on development. However this work fails to discuss the progress of women education and its impact. Kuldeep Kaur's (*Education in India 1781-1985: Policies, Planning and Implementation*, CRIDD, Chandigarh,1985) work deals with the development, growth and implementation made in the field of education by a large number of committees, conferences, seminars, study groups, study teams, panels, dispatches, minutes and the commissions appointed by the government of India, state, numerous advisory bodies. Author has arranged her work according to different aspects and highlights the education policy and planning in colonial India, as well as in free India. In her work the author has studied women education, technical education, teacher

education, and education of scheduled castes, rural and religious policy. The work highlights the education system in India, which however fails to discuss the system of education at state level.

Geraldine Forbes's work (*Women in Modern India* Cambridge University Press, New Delhi, 1998) gives a sympathetic and comprehensive study of Indian women. The author begins with reform movements for women and their impact. The women participation for legal rights and in the nationalist movement in the north and southern parts of India is also mentioned. Various women of North India mainly of Punjab have been named but it is not a complete study of women in colonial Punjab. The book tries to clear the concepts relating to the gender studies and gives a picture of women of India in general. Mukta Gupta (*Women and Education Development*, Sarup & Sons Publication, New Delhi, 2003) in his work provides information relating to women and their development, in various fields. The book highlights the higher educational development, growth of institutes, enrolment and faculty. The author examines the government plans for women education and careers of women. It also shows the effect of education on women, as socio-economic indicators. Gupta examines the development of women in all states of India. This study touches very briefly on development of women education in Punjab. Amrit Walia's (*Development of Education and Social, Political Change in Punjab 1882-1947*, ABS Publication, Jalandhar, 2005) gives an account of the development of Primary, Secondary, Higher, Technical and Female Education in Punjab under the colonial rule and its effects on society and politics. The study shows the effect of female education development in social and political. She has also highlighted the role of Christian Missionaries, socio-religious organization like the Arya Samaj, Singh Sabha and the women education development in Punjab. Kamlesh Mohan's (*Towards Gender History*, Aakar Book, Delhi, 2007) is an important source of information with special reference to the Punjab. It has the collection of six essays discussing different aspects of the women. The status and position of the women from Gurus period to the colonial rule has been discussed. Then it also mentions the importance of vernacular journal 'Stree Darpan' in fashioning the minds and images of the women. The book discusses some of the areas of concern of the research work but it is not a complete study of the women in colonial Punjab. Praneet Heyer's (*Women in Colonial Punjab(1901-1947)*, Ph.D. Thesis, Punjabi University, Patiala) study attempts to critically analyze women's emancipation, development and education during British colonial rule in Punjab. She has studied the journey of working women as a student. She believes that the emphasis on girls' education before the arrival of the British was limited to religious knowledge only. But after the British, with the efforts of the colonial rulers, people tried to widen the scope of girls' education. Mini Sandhu article 'Comparative Analysis of the *Panchal Pandita* and the *Punjabi Bhain* from a Gender Perspective' *International Journal of Punjab Studies*, vol-20(1), 2013, Focuses on the study of two Punjab periodicals of the early twentieth century. She explains the feminist outlook of reform movements in colonial Punjab. She analyzed that the Arya Samaj among the Hindus and the Singh Sabhas among the Sikhs, were the first to take up the challenge of educating and 'improving' the social status of their women. This paper analyses their periodicals, from the perspective of their male and female contributors, their dominant concerns and the underlying assumptions and values regarding the relative position and role of women in society.

Main Text

They tried to create awareness among women through different mediums of tracts and newspapers. They advanced the argument that without educated mothers; the Sikhs would continue to be mired in superstition, ignorance and immoral practices.[1] Education among women has become essential for development and their role as nation builders. They felt that it was important for both women and men to be educated for their glorious heritage. The leaders of the Singh Sabha, Chief Khalsa Diwan and the Sikh activists went along way in bringing about the awareness in their community about women education. They were unanimous against the social taboos that had reduced the status of women. They felt that if women remain immersed in ignorance, there can be no moral, social and intellectual progress in the society. Social reformers believed that if a community wanted healthy, honest and selfless members, the surest and easiest way was to have a literate woman in the home. The hand, head and heart of Punjabi girls and women should be evenly and harmoniously cultivated, so that they may discharge with grace and efficiency the duties of whatever stations of life they belong to, as wives or mothers or responsible members of society.[2] An important period in the history of the Sikh educational movement began with the foundation of the Chief Khalsa Diwan's Sikh Educational Conference. The motto of the Sikh Educational Conference was to provide education to every Sikh boy and girl without any discrimination. It has worked for the education of not only boys but also girls, for whom a large number of educational institutions have been established. It can be said that one of the objectives of the Sikh Educational Conference was to promote female education among the Sikhs.[3] Working towards its objective, the conference made major efforts for the expansion of women's education in the state. In the first session of the conference held at Gujranwala in April 1908, Sardar Shivdev Singh Oberoi emphasized on 'education of Sikh women'. The annual sessions of the Sikh

Educational Conference have been an occasion of great public interest and enthusiasm. People from all walks of life participated in its proceedings. It became tradition that as the venue of the conference shifted from year to year, a Sikh education institution whether for boys or girls was usually its gift to the town where it was held.[4] The conference soon became a source of inspiration for the Sikhs. Schools spread rapidly throughout Punjab. It is a fact that before the start of Sikh Educational Conference in 1908 there were only 07 Khalsa schools and with the efforts of Sikh Educational Conference this number reached 340 in 1947. Apart from this, many handicapped schools, schools for orphans, blind and handicapped were also opened and over two dozen libraries and literary associations also came up.[5] At the conference stages intellectuals and activists appealed the masses to come forward for the cause of women education. So many protagonists came and brought with themselves Sikh *kanya pathshalas*, sometimes with boarding houses. Sardar Shivdev Singh, Honorary Secretary of Educational Committee founded Khalsa *Kanya Middle Pathshala* at Sialkot in 1907 which he ran 25 years and borne the whole expenditure.[6] Another activist Kaur Singh started Guru Nanak *Kanya Pathshala* with 64 girls on roll at Sukho, Rawalpindi on November 16, 1910. It was served by his wife and two other women. They provided knowledge of handicrafts to girls along with basic instructions.[7] There was a Sikh *kanya* school in Rawalpindi. It had a boarding house for the far lived girls. The school also provided free education and accommodation for girls. For first time free books and slates were given to the girls. For monthly meal five rupees were charged.[8] On the same lines a Sikh *kanya pathshala (1912)* was started at Qadian. It had boarding house for outsider girls. Needle work was also taught.[9] The organizers of the Education Conference were sometimes publicly requested by the people of the particular area to open schools for girls. As a result Sikh *Kanya Pathshala* was opened at Doshanj Kalan, district Jalandhar. There were eight to ten schools for boys in the area, but not a single school for girls. The protagonists of girls' education Sardar Shivdev Singh and Kaur Singh, therefore, took debt for the building of the *pathshala*. The Sikhs living outside the country also contributed for the building. Maharaja Patiala and a contractor Sher Singh of Sandwan also contributed rupees 1000 each. Government grant of rupees 400 per annum was also attached to it. A local committee ran the institution successfully. Later on it started boarding house for the girls coming from faraway places. The institution became famous under the management and secretary ship of Bhai Kartar Singh who collected money from the countries like Burma. He left the government job and made a *jatha* of ladies including his family members for the cause.[10] It remained a famous institution of the *doaba*. Sardar Narayan Singh served the school as Incharge Manager and Sabhdra Devi as Head Mistress. The visit of Sardar Kartar Singh made the people of Burma remained in touch with its affairs for many years. In 1917, a person Sardar Kundan Singh sent rupee 1500 for the institution as financial aid.[11] The district Inspector Jalandhar Hemraj visited the *pathshala* on October 13, 1916. He went to conduct an examination. He admired that registers of the school were well organized. The building of Doshanj Kalan school was located at good place and airy. He also praised the boarding house for the girls and noticed that besides education, the girls were taught needle work, cooking and well organized in preparing and serving *langar* managed that turn by turn, 13 October, 1916.[12] Many visitors came to the school and admired its building and arrangements. Once Sohan Singh, a sub-overseer from Burma visited the school on June 23, 1917. He found its building and boarding airy and well maintained and appreciated the service of Bhai Kartar Singh who was managing the school. He also praised the intelligence and good nature of the Headmistress and noticed that she treated the girls as her daughters. The girls were provided not only with good education but also taught stitching and cooking.

The Sikh Educational Conference provided great encouragement for the expansion of educational institutions for women. The girls being educated, were bound to help in social upliftment. Education had begun to break down the seclusion nor the *Pardah*. Women began to attend Educational Conference and more significantly, took an active part like donating ornaments to help in the spread of education. By the year 1913, there were one Sikh *Kanya Mahavidyala* Ferozepur, 7 *kanya* Middle Schools and 60 *kanya* Primary schools for women.[13]

Table - 1

A list of Sikh educational institutions working under the management of Educational Committee of Chief Khalsa Diwan.[14]

Education Level	School for Boys	School for Girls
Primary School	50	60
Middle School	16	07

High School	08	01
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Source: Educational Committees of Chief Khalsa Diwan

The figure shows that the Sikhs remained forward in the field of primary education of girls than boys for whom 60 schools were established. The figure also shows that they took more interest to impart elementary education to women than higher. Primary education for girls was one of the theoretical questions of the time and was clearly needed. The Sikh Educational Conference set a goal that every village should have at least one primary school. Such a goal could not be easily achieved. They realized the importance of Sikh religion and religious training in the life of a girl especially at the early stage. To open *kanya pathshalas* in every town and village of the province was their ideal. There were a number of such customs and rituals that created hindrance in the progress of girls' education. Among these were the custom of early marriages, housekeeping and duties, and the practice of veiling. Due to social and religious conservatism, there was apathy of the people towards the education of girls.[15] There was also a fear among the people that the spread of education among women would replace the existing domestic squalor, dissatisfaction with the existing limited conditions of life, unnecessary freedom of thought and extravagance in life. Another fear was that educated girls might be unfit for domestic life, that they might be alienated from the tasks that are the dignity and pride of orthodox Punjabi women.[16] The need to prepare suitable curriculum for girl students, lack of qualified female teachers and lack of religious education was felt. The government and socio-religious reform bodies had been working enthusiastically in this direction to make the girls' education popular. It was noted in the Education Report of 1905-06 that the old prejudices against educating women were breaking down, and urban middle class Punjabis were becoming more eager to send their daughters to schools, to keep them there to a later stage, to pay fees for their education, even to send them to boardinghouses. The tide had begun to turn and people had begun to show interest for educating girls by lending their houses rent-free and offering prizes and sweet meats at annual functions.[17] Boarding girls schools became popular. In the past, parents had shown unnatural reluctance to send their girls away to school. But a great change occurred now that it became difficult to provide girls hostels to meet the ever increasing demand.[18] Reformers of this period emphasized the diversity of the curriculum for girls and said that it should not be assumed that the instruction suitable for boys should be good for Punjabi girls. They recommended that the syllabus for girls' primary school should be simpler than that for boys. The Sikh reformers were extra careful in preparing the syllabi for girls at the primary levels. They kept in mind the utility of it for the future of women. It was felt by the scholars that the curriculum should be designed in such a way as to enable the students to follow the duties and responsibilities of domestic and civic life. All faculties of scholars should be developed and trained to the maximum so that they feel that knowledge is a pleasure and not a chore.[19] They stressed upon religious education for women to transmit religious and moral values to the children of the community. They also advocated that the skills of home science like cooking, nursing and tailoring should also be taught to women. In addition to basic literacy, the girls should learn sewing, embroidery, cooking, music, poetry, games, arithmetic, hygiene and literature of Sikh religion. To train them in these areas, separate classes were arranged in middle and high schools. The people were becoming conscious to educate their daughters for the very reason to find good matches for them. Women themselves wanted to get education for many reasons, as child widows they wanted self honor and dignity. Women were interested in education because they loved economic and social freedom and there were some who really interested in gaining knowledge.[20] A report on the progress of education in the Punjab at the close of the quinquennium 1921-22 records the most significant increase in the number of Swadeshi or elementary schools for girls. It refers the statement of the Chief Inspectors, Even in the villages and remote districts the earlier indifference or hostility towards the improvement of women's intelligence and condition was disappearing. The Punjab was particularly fortunate in having a large number of private schools which were supported by private bodies of every denomination. Efforts of the activists had begun to yield results. The report of the Education Committee of the Chief Khalsa Diwan observed that the percentage of literate women among Sikhs increased from 1.2 to 2.7 in 1921 and increased to 4.9 percent in 1943.[21] The intellectuals of other communities also started paying special attention to the advancement of education among the Sikhs. They visited and participated in various sessions of Sikh Educational Conferences and noted the achievements of the conferences. Sir Louis William Dane, the Lieutenant Governor of Punjab, said in 1913 that education among Sikhs developed only because of Sikh educational conferences. The important thing was that they were fully aware about the education of their women. The women education among Sikhs progressed rapidly. The *Khalsa Samachar* noted the statement of Lieutenant Governor in Gurmukhi language.[22] Education Department of Punjab wrote in the Punjab Education Report of 1914-1915 that "In all the districts of Punjab the activities of the Sikh Educational Committee were being felt. The Educational Committee of the Chief Khalsa Diwan was working strenuously to disseminate education

among the Sikh community.”[23] In 1920 Lieutenant Governor of Punjab Sir Edward Menglegun popularly known as *lat sahib* noted as, “I have been much struck on my return to the province after an absence of some years to see how generously the Sikh community now supports the cause of education. Wherever I go I see Khalsa schools almost all quite new, well built and well founded which have been provided by the liberality of the panth.”[24] Educational Committee of Chief Khalsa Diwan opened many primary, middle and high schools for boys and girls. Sikhs were quite advance in comparison to other communities in the Punjab in case of the primary education of girls. In 1928 the number of primary schools went upto 82 which covered almost the whole state like Peshawar, Attack, Jhelum, Gujarat, Shahpur, Lahore, Amritsar, Gurdaspur, Lyallpur, Montgomery, Ambala, Rawalpindi, Hoshiarpur, Ludhiana etc.[25] Majority of the schools were established in Sindh Sagar *doab*, areas included Rawalpindi, Jhelum and Attack. The number of schools here was twenty-five. Earlier this area was under the influence of Baba Khem Singh Bedi who established 108 *kanya pathshalas* by 1880s. He Campaigned for girls' education and succeeded in establishing a large number of girls' schools in both Jhelum and Rawalpindi.[26] Due to the efforts of Baba Khem Singh Bedi the area of Sindh Sagar *doab* remained forward in primary education of girls. In Bari *doab* and Chaj *doab* the number of schools was nineteen and fourteen respectively followed by Trans-Indus with 8 schools and Cis-Satluj with 6 schools. In Bist Jalandhar *doab* there was only one school in Hoshiarpur. These *kanya pathshalas* generally named as Guru Nanak Kanya Pathshalas, Gurmat Kanya Pathshalas, Sikh Kanya Pathshalas, Khalsa Kanya Pathshalas. Some where they were named with the name of some women like Mata Bhag Devi Kanya Pathshala, Bajuragwal (Gujarat) and Mata Sahib Kaur Kanya Pathshala, Neela (Jhelum). There is one interesting thing that there were some schools which opened for the girls of special castes like Aror Bans Gurmat Kanya Pathshala, *muhalla* Kareempura, Peshawar and Majbian Di Kanya Pathshala, Jethuwal, Amritsar.[27] The importance of religion and of religious training in the life of a girl has been emphasized, especially at the primary stage. The syllabus of primary girls' schools was made carefully keeping these things in mind. Medium of the instruction was Punjabi language. Emphasis was given to Gurmukhi and religion. Urdu was taught in the 3rd class. Besides, some knowledge of Maths and Geography was also given.[28] In 1913, the number of such schools was 60. In the year 1933, the number increased to 126 and it reached up to 189 in 1946.

YEAR	1913	1928	1930	1931	1932	1933	1934	1935	1946
No. of Schoo	60	82	91	108	124	126	131	145	189

Source: Reports of Educational Committees of Chief Khalsa Diwan

The table further indicates that the number of girls' schools raised more than three times between the years 1913 and 1946. Increase in the middle schools for the girls was not as rapid as it was in case of primary schools. From 1913 to 1931 the increase in number of middle schools was only four. In 1913 there were 7 middle schools which rose upto 12 in 1931. After 15 years the number of middle schools went up to 36 in 1946. It was good success. The prominent schools were Guru Nanak Kanya Pathshala, Chakwal (Jehlum), Guru Nanak Kanya Pathshala, Amritsar, Girls Oriental College, Jaspaloan (Ludhiana) and Rukmani Girls' School, Haripur (Hazara).[29]

Guru Nanak Kanya Pathshala, Amritsar remained famous for its religious instructions. Once Shri Mool Ji (religious leader) visited the school and praised its management. He stated that Gurmukhi was the medium of instruction in the school. English was taught in higher classes.[30] Building was airy and clean. One of the important features of the school was that it was managed entirely by women. The Chief Inspector reported in the Report on Progress of Education in the Punjab during the Quinquennial ending 1921-22 that “even where ladies committees exist, the ladies had not shown any interest to take an active part in the management of schools. There was fortunately one exception and that was Guru Nanak Kanya Pathshala at Amritsar. It was managed entirely by women so far as domestic affairs of the school were concerned.”[31] The middle classes started from 4th standard. These were known as first middle, second middle, third middle, fourth middle and fifth middle. Syllabus of middle classes was divided into two parts, reading and writing. In the first middle reading *Guru Singh Itihas*, *Sukhmani*, *Japuji Sahib*, *Dhulhan Patrika* and Grammar were taught. In second middle reading, students were taught Hindu scriptures like half portion of *Hanuman Natak*, half part of *Vidaya Ratnakar* and *Viakaran Parsang*. In 3rd middle reading 3rd and 4th *pothi* on Punjabi language and *Arog Niyamawali* were studied. In 4th middle 5th and 6th *pothi* on Punjabi language, remaining part of *Arog Niyamawali* and in 5th middle class remaining part of 6th *pothi* on Punjabi language, *Binay Patrika* and last part of grammar were taught.[32] In the writing parts students studied many subjects. In first middle class they learned to write letters or applications and dictation; decimal system, interest, proportional and

square area in Maths; Geography of Punjab, India and Europe; History of India (first part), and *Sughar Bibi* in Hygiene Physiology. Cutting and stitching of cloths were also taught. The syllabus was upgraded in the next classes. In second middle students were taught to write letters and proverbs. Geography of Africa, America and Asia was studied. Remaining parts of history of India and *Sughar Bibi* was completed and girls were also trained in stitching and needle work. In 3rd middle class students learned the Geography of districts of Punjab; in 4th and 5th middle Geography of Punjab, India, Asia and world was taught. English was taught in all middle classes and Hindi was introduced in 5th middle standard.[33] The table explains it further:

The higher education among Sikh women was even less than primary and middle education. Till 1932 there was only one high school, Sikh Kanya Mahavidyala Ferozepur and it was also a famous boarding school. The boarding housed married, unmarried and widowed women from India and abroad. The number of high schools went upto four in 1936.

The other high schools were Guru Nanak Kanya Pathshala, Amritsar, Gobind Girls High School, Abtbad and Sri Guru Hargobind Ujagar Hari Sikh Girls School, Sidwan Khurd, Ludhiana.[34] The number of students was more in Guru Nanak Kanya Pathshala, Amritsar but in quality, popularity and glory wise no one could surpass the Sikh Kanya Mahavidyala, Ferozepur.[35] There were recognized primary, middle and high classes in Sikh Kanya Mahavidyala. Gurmukhi was taught from first standard and Urdu from ninth standard. English was also taught. There were total 312 students resided in the *ashram* from various places like Punjab, U.P, Bengal, Madras, Delhi, Sindh, Bombay, Burma, Africa, Port Blair and Malaya etc. Lectures of scholars were held in the institution from time to time to enrich the existing knowledge of the girls. Trips were also arranged for them.[36] There were 291 and 622 girls were studying respectively in the Gobind High School, Abtbad and Guru Nanak Kanya Pathshala, Amritsar. Cooking, stitching and *rag* education were a part of syllabus of Amritsar School. Sikh Girls School, Sidwan Khurd, Ludhiana was famous in district Ludhiana. It was started by Bhai Narain Singh as a primary school at his village Sidwan Khurd in 1909.[37] Bhai Sahib opened it in the memory of his only demised son. It raised up to middle standard in 1920s. It was boarding school. The wife of Bhai Sahib served the school as superintendent and widow daughter Harparkash Kaur as teacher. He donated his land and a well to the school and constructed a building within a part of his house. The family members of Bhai Sahib worked as honorary servants of the institution. Bhai Sahib registered the whole property of the institution in the name of '*panth*' and made a local committee to run the affairs of the institution.[38] The girls learned to make carpets, soaps, oils and the art of stitching, knitting, cooking, dying and fruit preservation along with basic instructions. One interesting fact was that sometime the students of institution went to the villages to teach those girls who could not come to school.[39] Considerable attention had been paid to the industrial training and handiwork for girls. Courses were made which were suited to the needs of the girls and to their environment. The improvement in handiwork was an illustration of the change.[40] Several kinds of works were done by the pupils. At the Sikh Educational Conferences these works were displayed for sale in separate rooms. In the exhibition of 9th Sikh Educational Conference special attention was paid by the visitors towards the clothes of daily use, *phulkaris* and other artifacts prepared by the girls of Sikh Kanya Mahavidyala Ferozepur, Guru Nanak Kanya Pathshala Amritsar and Kanya Pathshala Sukho, Rawalpindi. Among them a *kameez* prepared with hands by Bibi Jasondhanand a purse of pearls by a blind student of Sikh Kanya Mahavidyala Ferozepur, a statue of deer and peacock by Bibi Sushil Kaur of Amritsar and *phulkaris* by the girls of Sukho Kanya Pathshala were praised by visitors.[41] It was seen that general masses took more interest in the industrial training for their girls. The Khalsa *Dastkari* School Amritsar was fulfilling their needs. It was founded in 1913 through the efforts of Rai Bahadur Sardar Sadhu Singh one of the founder of the Chief Khalsa Diwan, with a view to impart training to women in cutting, tailoring, embroidery and other handicrafts. Later on, it was renamed as Teka Devi Industrial School after the name of Shrimati Teka Devi whose husband Sardar Mangal Singh had donated a big sum of money in the memory of his wife.[42] Till 1928 the 14 Sikh girls had been passed medical course from Christian Medical College, Ludhiana while 9 were studying there. 4 girls had been passed from Lady Harding College Delhi, while 8 were studying there.[43] The Sikh girl students of Lady Harding College also got scholarships from the endowment fund given by Rai Bahadur Sardar Narain Singh of Delhi.[44] The increase in the number of institutions naturally added to the financial responsibilities of the Educational Committee of the Chief Khalsa Diwan. Many institutions opened in temporary buildings without any permanent fund to run them. At the occasion of Educational Conference a national fund was raised to meet purpose. Appeals were made for funds at the annual sessions of the Sikh Educational Conference. The Educational Committee was vested with full control over the management of all collected funds.[45] Grants-in-aid were issued to Khalsa institutions from these funds. The Khalsa girls' schools affiliated to and receiving grants-in-aid from the Educational Committee of the Chief Khalsa Diwan from its fund.[46] The Educational Committee granted rupees 8589 to primary schools of boys and girls and rupees 3048 to high, middle and lower middle schools of girls in 1931.[47] It was a fact that the speed at

which progress was made would have been impossible of achievement, if the Educational Conference had not been able to collect adequate funds for the purpose.[48] Sometimes, Sikh living in foreign countries sent financial help for the cause of education and the Chief Khalsa Diwan distributed that amount among various institutions. Once, aid of 300 rupees was received from many foreign countries, the Chief Khalsa Diwan distributed that amount at the meeting of its executive body as 15 rupees to Sikh Kanya Mahavidyala Ferozepur, 15 rupees to Khalsa *Bhujangan* boarding house, Kairon, 15 rupees to Sidhwan Khurd Girls' School, Ludhiana. The rest of amount distributed to various *kanya* schools according to their contribution towards society.[49] One of the greatest landmarks in the education of girls was achieved in 1940 when first college for Sikh girls was started at Lahore. The college started classes of *Bhudimani*, *Vidwani* and *Gyani*. The arrangement of teaching English with B.A was also there.[50] With the tremendous efforts of Educational Committee of Chief Khalsa Diwan the percentage of educated women increased. Sikh community ranked 2nd highest group in women literacy with 4.9% after Hindu with 4.46%.[51] The remarkable feature of these Khalsa institutions was that a number of Hindu, Muslim and children from the depressed class also studied there. The member of any community could send their girls to Khalsa institutions. For the growth of educational movement, some reformers wanted to impart *gurnat* and elementary knowledge to the children by establishing a number of primary schools. But it was not always possible to open schools exclusively for girls and boys. To solve this problem Sardar Dharam Singh; a contractor from Delhi came forward with the idea of co-educational institutions. It was the most economical method of educating the girls also. He viewed to impart *gurnat* and elementary knowledge to the children by establishing primary schools attached with village *dharmsalas*. [52] An idea came first time to propagate elementary education among the community at the 4th Sikh Educational Conference, Rawalpindi. A national fund was also raised for the purpose. In 1915, Educational Committee made a scheme to impart elementary education to the Sikh boys and girls through *Gurdwaras* and *Dharmsalas* of the villages. But the work was not done for next 10 years. In 1926 Sardar Bhadur Dharam Singh came forward with second scheme of elementary education.[53] He selected 19 members of the trust named as Guru Nanak Vidya Bhandar Trust and got it registered. An educational sub-committee of three members of the Trust was founded. Sardar Shivdev Singh, B.A, LLB, Honorary Secretary, Educational Committee Amritsar; Professor Jodh Singh, Khalsa College, Amritsar and Professor Teja Singh, Khalsa College, Amritsar were members of the sub-committee. Sardar Shivdev Singh was made administrative incharge of schools.[54] The Trust started its 16 schools in the neighboring villages of Amritsar in 1926. These schools were affiliated with Chief Khalsa Diwan and 4 to 5 more schools had submitted their affiliation forms for sanction in the same year.[55] The Chief Khalsa Diwan provided special help to run the schools. The syllabus sanctioned by the District Board was taught in the schools therefore District Board also gave them grants. Medium of instructions was in Gurmukhi script. Along with religious and Gurmukhi learning, Urdu, Maths and Geography were taught. Sometimes the students got middle school scholarships. The teachers of these schools were rewarded by the trust. Religious education was emphasized. *Shabdi jathas* were made in some schools.[56]

Guru Nanak Vidya Bhandar Trust Delhi worked immensely for the cause of education. It ran about hundred schools, propagated education for low caste people and opened an industrial school at Delhi.[57] Mostly these schools ran at village *dharmsalas* and historical *Gurdwaras*. Buildings of these schools were better than the schools of District Board. Once an Assistant District Inspector of schools, *tehsil* Jagraon, district Ludhiana wrote in the visitor book that the building of the school was well build and no building was equal to it in the Jagraon centre.[58] Small scale libraries for staff, students as well as for local people were also established in the premises of the schools. The Bhandar Trust sent books on Sikh History, General knowledge, periodicals on religion and education in such libraries. Bhandar Trust had made arrangements for the education of adults in Night schools. About sixty adults joined them to take lessons in their free time. [59] The Trust also contributed to run Junior Vernacular class for teachers training in the Khalsa College by providing financial help.[60] There were 73 men and women teachers working in Bhandar schools. Mostly teachers were qualified with normal or *gyani* classes. Some untrained teachers also worked as preachers. Women teachers generally belonged to the families of male teaching staff. Local bodies encouraged the wives of the school masters to become literate and join the teaching profession. Untrained women teachers gave training of stitching and knitting to the girl students. The teachers were paid by the Bhandar Trust.[61]

The number of these schools increased with the passage of time. The Guru Nanak Vidya Bhandar Trust also started schools for untouchable children in many villages.[62] One such school was running at Verka, district Amritsar where students were provided free stationary by the Trust.[63] Special emphasis was given to the handicraft works. Some of these schools maintain gardens of their own also, looked after by the students every day. Special classes of dyeing and printing clothes were started at Delhi.[64] Leather work was also taught there. All these handicraft items and fruits of the garden of Bhandar schools were exhibited at the Sikh Educational Conferences. At the Lahore Sikh

Educational Conference the schools of Bhandar trust displayed their works of art and craft at large scale. District Inspector of schools, Amritsar reported in detail the exhibition of these schools in the following: "This room was engaged by Sardar Amar Singh Secretary of the Guru Nanak Vidaya Bhandar Sabha, which maintains a number of primary schools, One printed Gurmukhi copy slip was placed alongside a manuscript copy written by one of the boys of these schools and it was very hard to distinguish between two. These schools have a system of co-education which has already proved a great success. Wooden and iron models teaching Gurmukhi letters had a very high educational value. Some of the exhibits included *kashida*, crochet, sewing and knitting work such as nice *phulkaries*, handkerchiefs, table clothes, pillow covers, mufflers, cushions, socks, boots and shirts etc. done by the girls and mistresses of these schools were highly appreciated. Fresh fruits, nice lemons, grapes and oranges were placed everyday in the room for display. Some specimens of carpentry works were also exhibited. The most interesting and fascinating exhibit was a specimen of the steamship prepared by the head teacher at Kirtangarh in the Amritsar District, which was kept, floating in a tub of water. This gave the spectators a general conception of a steamship." [65] The system of co-education of Bhandar schools proved a great success. In 1939 there were total 58 co-education schools of Bhandar Trust. 4 schools worked at U.P, one at Delhi and one at Guru Ki Kashi (Patiala State). 52 schools worked at the 9 districts of Punjab like Amritsar, Lahore, Gurdaspur, Jalandhar, Ludhiana, Hoshiarpur, Ambala, Hisar and Layalpur. The trust also worked for the adult education. "Of the 52 schools, 8 were night schools where instruction was given to adults. The total number of students of these schools was 3135. They were 1990 boys, 968 girls and 177 adults. The students admitted without any distinction of caste and creed. 2557 Sikhs, 205 Hindus, 320 Muslims and 53 untouchables were studying in these schools." [66] The good point was that the schools carried on co-education system and solved a difficult problem of the girls' education. About one thousand girls were studying in Bhandar schools. The Trust benefited the province both ways. It saved finance of the province as to establish separate schools for girls were heavy economic burden and also solved the problem of scarcity of women teachers for girls' schools. Guru Nanak Vidaya Bhandar Trust schools were appreciated by Education Department and newspapers of the time reflected this: *Phulwari*, Lahore appreciated the contribution of the trust in imparting education in a number of districts of Punjab. [67] Sacha *Sajjan Akhbar*, Amritsar noted the remarks of Commissioner of rural development on 8-3-1938 that trust schools were successfully run and these set an example for rural education. Deputy Commissioner of Ludhiana who happened to visit the Bhandar School remarked that Bhandar Khalsa schools were continuing to do well in making co-education popular in the villages. [68]

Conclusion

To sum up, the contribution of these individuals and organizations was immense. They faced many difficulties to deal the sensitive and responsible issue of girl's education. They took initial difficulties as challenges and took these difficulties as motivation to work harder. Result was positive. Although the number of institutions was not much, but the desire to teach their daughters and sisters was rising among the people. The realization was there that education of women was essential to the growth of the community and national progress. But the means to acquire it were limited. Financial stringency and lack of adequate staff has retarded the spread of women education. If there was apathy on the part of parents towards girls' education, some educationalist on their part too appeared to be reluctant to impart higher and professional education to them. They considered only primary, homely and religious education as whole educational plank from them. Till 1947, 36 middle schools, 4 high schools and one Sikh girls' college were established.

References

1. Doris R. Jakobsh, *Relocating Gender in Sikh History*, Oxford University press, New Delhi, 2003, p-132.
2. AmritWalia, *Development of Education and Social-Political Change in the Punjab 1882-1947*, ABS Publications, Jalandhar, 2005, p- 174.
3. Mohinder Singh, *History and Culture of Punjab*, Atlantic Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi, 1988, p- 122.
4. *Souvenir of Central Khalsa Orphanage*, Published by Bhag Singh Ankhai, Amritsar, pp-15-16, see also *Khalsa Samachar*, March 22, 1932, p- 3.
5. Ganda Singh, "Sikh Educational Conference", *The Punjab Past and Present*, Punjabi University, Patiala, 1973, p- 76.
6. *Silver Jubilee Book*, Chief Khalsa Diwan, Amritsar, 1935, p- 81.
7. *Khalsa Samachar*, November 23, 1911, p- 5.
8. *Ibid.*, February 16, 1911, p- 6.
9. *Ibid.*, June 20, 1912, p- 7.
10. *Ibid.*, June 20, 1912, pp- 3-6.
11. *bid.*, July 19, 1917 p-, 4.
12. *Ibid.*, November 23, 1916, p- 7.
13. *Ibid.*, June 12, 1913, p- 5.
14. *Ibid.*, July 5, 1917, p- 4.
15. Sanaullah Khan, "Girls' Education in the Punjab", *The Punjab Past and Present*,

- Punjabi University, Patiala.1973,p-127
16. AmritWalia, *Op.cit*,p- 176.
 17. Shyamala Bhatia, *Social Change and Politics in Punjab (1898-1910)*,Enkay Publishers,Delhi,1987,pp-59-60.
 18. *Report on the Progress of Education in the Punjab during the Quinquennium ending 1921-22*, p-129.
 19. AmritWalia, *op.cit*,p- 182.
 20. *Phulwari*, July 1935,p- 666.
 21. *Report of Educational Committee of Chief Khalsa Diwan*, 1943,
 22. *Khalsa Samachar*, April 24, 1913,p- 3.
 23. *Khalsa Samachar*, May 4, 1916,p- 3.
 24. *Ibid.*, May 12, 1920,p- 3.
 25. *Report of Educational Committee of Chief Khalsa Diwan of the Year 1928*, Amritsar,pp- 195-199.
 26. *Gazetteer of the Rawalpindi District, 1883-84*, The Civil and Military Gazetts Press, Lahore,pp- 55-56.
 27. *Report of Educational Committee of Chief Khalsa Diwan of the Year 1928*, Amritsar, pp-195-199.
 28. *Guru Nanak Vidya Bhandar Trust de Schoolain Sambandhi Sankhep Report*, Published in the *Report of Educational Committee,Chief Khalsa Diwan*, Amritsar, 1934,pp- 80-81.
 29. *Report of the Educational Committee of Chief Khalsa Diwan, 1928*, p-191.
 30. *Khalsa Samachar*, January 29, 1914, p- 6.
 31. *Report on the Progress of Education in the Punjab during the Quinquennium Ending 1921-22*,p- 133.
 32. *Monthly Progress Report of the Girls Middle School Kairon, April 1910-March 1911*, n.p.
 33. *Ibid*
 34. *26th Sikh Educational Conference Di Report, 1936*,pp- 18-19.
 35. *Educational Committee, Chief Khalsa Diwan De Varshik Report 1938*, pp-67-69.
 36. *Ibid.*
 37. *Punjab District Gazetteers, Ludhiana*, 1970,p- 533.
 38. *Khalsa Samachar*, 16 May, 1932,p- 1.
 39. *Educational Committee, Chief Khalsa Diwan De Varshik Report 1938*,pp-67-69.
 40. *Report on the Progress of Education in the Punjab during the Quinquennium Ending 1921-1922*, p-129.
 41. *Khalsa Samachar*, May 4, 1916,p- 2.
 42. *Souvenir of the Central Khalsa Orphanage*, Amritsar,p- 19.
 43. *Report of Educational Committee Chief Khalsa Diwan*, Amritsar 1928,p- 62.
 44. *Khalsa Samachar*, September 14, 1916,p- 5.
 45. Fauja Singh, "Sikh Educational Conference,"*The Panjab Past and Present*, vol.xvi-2,October, 1982p- 375.
 46. *Brief Report of Educational Committee Chief Khalsa Diwan for the year of 1926*,Amritsar - 19.
 47. *Khalsa Samachar*, April 30, 1931,p-4
 48. Fauja Singh, *op.cit.*,p- 379.
 49. *Chief Khalsa Diwan Di Karvai (1911-1919)*, Vol 2, Chief Khalsa Diwan, Amritsar,p- 61.
 50. *Khalsa Samachar*, September 26, 1940,p- 7.
 51. *Report of Educational Committee of Chief Khalsa Diwan*, Amritsar 1946, p-7
 52. *Khalsa Samachar*, November 16, 1933,p 7.
 53. *Ibid.*,p- 6.
 54. *Guru Nanak VidayaBhandar Trust de SchoolainSambandiSenkhep Report,1926*, p-79.
 55. *Brief Report of Educational Committee of Chief KhalsaDiwan for the year of 1926*,pp- 5-6, also see *KhalsaSamachar*, May12, 1927,p- 2.
 56. *Guru Nanak Vidya Bhandar Trust de Schoolian Sambandi Senkhep Report,1926*, p-80-81.
 57. *Golden Jubilee Book*, Educational Committee, Chief Khalsa Diwan, Amritsar (1908-1958) De Panjah Saal Da Itihas, Amritsar, 1958, p-16.
 58. *Guru Nanak Vidaya Bhandar Trust de Schoolain Sambandi Senkhep Report,1926*,p-81.
 59. *Ibid.*, 81-82.
 60. *Khalsa Samachar*, April 21, 1932,p- 3.
 61. *Guru Nanak Vidaya Bhandar Trust de Schoolain Sambandi Senkhep Report*, 83-84.
 62. *Khalsa Samachar*, April 21, 1932,p- 3.
 63. *Guru Nanak Vidaya Bhandar Trust de Schoolain Sambandi Senkhep Report,1926*, p-83.

64. *Khalsa Samachar*, 21 April, 1932,p- 3.
65. *Guru Nanak VidyaBhandar Trust de Schoolian Sambandi Senkeph Report*, 1926,pp- 82-83.
66. *Khalsa Samachar*, July 20, 1939,pp- 8-9.
67. *Guru Nanak Vidaya Bhandar Trust de Schoolian Sambandi Sankhep Report*,1926, p- 85.
68. *Summary Report of the Conference of Guru Nanak Vidaya Bhandar Trust Schools*, 14-15 April 1938, Published in *Khalsa Samachar*, May 26, 1938,p- 10.